

Sidewalk width measurement using street view images and spatial data analysis

Hoda Allahbakhshi^{*1,2}, and Alireza Harrafamoughin^{†1,2}

University of Zurich, ¹Digital Society Initiative, ²Department of Geography

GISRUK 2025

Summary

Accessible sidewalks are crucial for fostering inclusive cities, especially for individuals with mobility impairments. Sidewalk width is key to accessibility, as narrow sidewalks can create barriers for certain groups such as wheelchair users. Accurate measurement and mapping of sidewalk width are essential for mobility and navigation. In this paper, we apply two methods for sidewalk width measurement: one using street view imagery and another based on spatial data analysis. Our results indicate that the spatial data analysis method provides broader coverage and more accurate width information. Additionally, it can serve as a basis for generating further accessibility data, such as vertical and cross-slope.

KEYWORDS: sidewalk accessibility, width, street view imagery, spatial data analysis, mobility-impaired

1. Introduction

Accessible pedestrian infrastructure is essential for promoting inclusive cities, particularly for individuals with mobility impairments. Sidewalk width is a critical factor, influencing walkability, wheelchair maneuvering, and overall pedestrian comfort. Narrow sidewalks can create barriers particularly for wheelchair users and individuals with mobility aids, limiting their ability to navigate urban spaces independently. To support inclusive urban planning, reliable sidewalk width data is crucial for assessing compliance with accessibility standards and identifying areas that require infrastructure improvements (Pinhão et al., 2022).

Despite its significance, sidewalk width data is often incomplete or inaccurate due to limitations in traditional measurement methods. Manual field surveys can be time-consuming and prone to human error, while satellite and aerial imagery may not capture detailed sidewalk-level features (Hosseini et al., 2021). Recent advancements in geospatial technologies, such as GIS-based analysis and computer vision techniques, offer promising alternatives for automating sidewalk width measurements and improving data accuracy. These approaches leverage street-level imagery, point cloud data, and machine learning to extract detailed sidewalk attributes, enhancing the precision of sidewalk network mapping (Pinhão et al., 2022).

In this study, we aim to apply two approaches for sidewalk width measurement in the study area of District 1 of the City of Zurich, one based on street view images and another based on spatial data analysis. By comparing the two methods, we explore the implications of these approaches for enhancing future sidewalk accessibility feature enrichment. Also, by leveraging advanced geospatial technologies, we aim to provide a more accurate and comprehensive understanding of sidewalk accessibility, paving the way for more inclusive and efficient urban infrastructure development.

* Hoda.allahbakhshi@dsi.uzh.ch

† Alireza.harrafamoughin@uzh.ch

2. Data

For sidewalk width measurement, polygons related to sidewalk or footway infrastructure were extracted from the land cover data of the Official Cadastral Surveying – Data Model ZH (Standard) (OGD) (Stadt Zurich, 2024a). District boundaries from Open Data Zurich were also used to filter the dataset to ensure that only data from the study area was included (Stadt Zurich, 2024b).

3. Methodology

3.1. Width measurement based on Street View Images (W-SVI)

Within the ZuriACT project (Allahbakhshi, 2023), an extended version of the *Infra3D* software (Infra3d web-client, 2024) developed by iNovitas, 2024 was used. The extended version included additional layers for data collection and data validation, inspired by the Project Sidewalk tool (Saha et al., 2019). In addition to the point accessibility features provided by Project Sidewalk such as *curb ramps*, and *obstacles in the path*, three line features were added, focusing on *sidewalk width*, *cross slope*, and *vertical slope* measurement.

Six individuals, including us with expertise in geographical knowledge, contributed to the line features data collection and validation. Each person was assigned different data collection zones within District 1 of the City of Zurich. Following the instructions, we logged into the Infra3D tool and began measuring the sidewalk width at the outset of each sidewalk using Street View Imagery (SVI), (see Fig.1). As we progressed, we clicked through the SVI and visually reassessed the sidewalk width whenever an obstacle reduced it to less than 180 cm, which is the standard sidewalk width according to the Swiss standard guideline. If no obstacles were present and the sidewalk infrastructure remained unchanged (i.e., the width was consistent), we remeasured the width every five clicks on the SVIs, which corresponded to approximately a few meters on the ground. Each width measurement was validated by a second expert to ensure accuracy.

Figure 1 Sidewalk width measurement using Infra3D tool in District 1 of Zurich; the green lines represent the collected width data

However, width measurement errors occurred because it was difficult to ensure that the lines were drawn perpendicular to the sidewalk based on the SVI alone. To improve accuracy, the orthophoto background was used to verify line placement. Despite this, some errors in width measurement remained. Additionally, the lack of sidewalk visibility and occlusions made it impossible to measure

sidewalk width when the view was obstructed. Also, when the sidewalk was visible from only one angle or camera, accurate measurements were challenging. Besides, there were gaps in the SVI coverage within District 1, which limited the ability to measure sidewalk width in those areas. For future data analysis, such as enriching the sidewalk network with accessibility information, these gaps could pose a problem and need to be addressed using different approaches, such as interpolation. Finally, the width measurements relied on expert knowledge, so human errors or inconsistencies between data collected by different experts may have occurred.

3.2. Width measurement based on spatial data analysis (W-SDA)

To reduce width measurement inaccuracies, fill the gaps, and also semi-automate the width measurement process, we implemented the following approach so-called W-SDA based on open geographical data:

The sidewalk polygons introduced in the data section were used to generate width information using QGIS software version 3.34.11. To achieve this, we first utilized the BecaGIS QGIS Plugin (version 24.10.21), which enhances QGIS by providing advanced geoprocessing tools, including vector analysis functions such as generating skeletons or medial axes of polygons (Quach & Giudiceandrea, 2024). These medial axes help determine polygon centerlines, which serve as a basis for drawing perpendicular lines to extract width information. However, when polygons were not rectangular, the medial axis became more complex. For example, irregularly shaped or concave polygons—such as L-shaped ones—resulted in incorrect centerlines, Fig. 2a.

Figure 2 (a): Polygon centerline created by BecaGIS tool, (b): Baselines for width measurement

To address this issue, we manually and visually reviewed the polygons. Whenever the generated centerlines were incorrect, we redrew them using the *Add line features tool* in QGIS, Fig. 2b. From this point, we refer to the corrected centerlines as *baselines* because not all of them occurred in the centerline of the polygon but were inside the polygon and served as a baseline for drawing perpendicular lines.

Using the QGIS library, we developed a Python script in Visual Studio Code (version 1.96.4) that includes a Graphical User Interface (GUI) as shown in Figure 3. The input data consists of the desired sidewalk segment size (set to one meter), the distance from the baseline, (i.e., *Offset Length* set to 10 meters), sidewalk polygons, and baselines. These parameters are used to generate perpendicular lines to the baseline. Once generated, the perpendicular lines that extended beyond the polygon boundary were automatically clipped. Additionally, if any drawn lines cross over into another polygon, a key ID (created for each perpendicular line, polygon, and baseline) ensures that they are removed. This process results in width data at the desired sidewalk segment size that can be adjusted depending on the data application.

Figure 3 Graphical User Interface developed for width measurement based on Spatial Data Analysis

4. Results

The width data generated by the W-SVI and W-SDA methods are shown in Fig. 4a. The W-SVI-based data includes 14,226 data points, while the W-SDA includes 48482. The primary reason for this difference is that the W-SDA generated width data at a finer segment size of 1 meter. Additionally, the W-SVI approach relies on SVI, which has gaps in the study area. Furthermore, the placement accuracy of the width data in W-SDA is better than that of the W-SVI method. For example, the zoomed-in section in Fig. 4b shows that despite using orthophotos, the widths generated by W-SVI are not always perpendicular to the sidewalks.

Figure 4 (a): Width data generated by W-SVI in blue and by W-SDA in orange, (b)

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we applied two methods for measuring sidewalk width. Our initial results suggest that the W-SDA method offers broader coverage and more accurate width information. In the next phase, we will conduct a more in-depth comparison between the width data generated by these two methods. Our

comparison will focus on assessing the accuracy and time efficiency of both approaches. We hypothesize that the spatial data analysis method will be more efficient, as the most time-consuming part of the process is creating the baselines, which we aim to automate further. However, once the width data are generated, this method allows for the extraction of further features beneficial for sidewalk accessibility by incorporating additional information. For instance, by applying a Digital Elevation Model (DEM), we can assign elevation data to the width lines and calculate the cross slope. Furthermore, by drawing perpendicular lines to the width data, we can create accurate centerlines, which are useful for applications like pedestrian routing. By assigning elevation information to the start and end points of these centerlines, we can also calculate the vertical slope for the desired sidewalk segments. With this approach, we can enrich accessibility data at a larger scale, providing a more reliable basis for sidewalk accessibility assessments and promoting urban inclusivity.

6. Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the University of Zurich, the Digital Society Initiative, the Smart City Zurich Innovation Credit, and the Digitalization Initiative of Zurich Higher Education Institutions (DIZH) for partially financing this research. Our gratitude also goes to the ZuriACT team and participants for their invaluable contributions.

References

- Allahbakhshi, H. (2023). Towards an Inclusive Urban Environment: A Participatory Approach for Collecting Spatial Accessibility Data in Zurich, in: 12th International Conference on Geographic Information Science (GIScience 2023). Schloss Dagstuhl-Leibniz-Zentrum für Informatik, Leeds.
- Hosseini, M., et al. (2021). Sidewalk measurements from satellite images: Preliminary findings. arXiv preprint arXiv:2112.06120.
- Infra3d web-client, (2024). URL: <https://infra3d.ch/>
- iNovitas, (2024). URL: <https://www.inovitas.ch/>
- Saha, M., et al. (2019). Project Sidewalk: A Web-based Crowdsourcing Tool for Collecting Sidewalk Accessibility Data at Scale, in: Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems - Proceedings. Association for Computing Machinery. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3290605.3300292>
- Stadt Zurich. (2024a). Amtliche Vermessung - Datenmodell ZH (Standard) (OGD) (kantonaler Datensatz) Retrieved September 7, 2024, from <https://www.stadt-zuerich.ch/geodaten/download/10016?format=128>
- Stadt Zurich. (2024b). Stadtkreise. Retrieved September 7, 2024, from https://data.stadt-zuerich.ch/dataset/geo_stadtkreise
- Quach, T., and Giudiceandrea, A., (2024), BecaGIS GeoProcessing Tools for QGIS, URL: <https://github.com/thangqd/becagis/>
- Pinhão, C.F, et al. (2022). Determining Accessible Sidewalk Width by Extracting Obstacle Information from Point Clouds. , arXiv preprint. Available at: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2211.04108>.

Biographies

Hoda Allahbakhshi is an Academic Associate at the Digital Society Initiative and Group Leader of the «Inclusive Mobility and Sustainable Transport» research group at the Department of Geography, UZH. Her current research focuses on human mobility and accessibility analytics, with an emphasis on underserved population groups such as mobility-disabled or -restricted persons.

Alireza Harrafamoughin holds a Master's degree in Geographic Information Systems & Remote Sensing (GIS/RS) and is a GIS specialist. His research interests focus on cutting-edge technologies and innovations in the field of GIS, particularly in spatial data analysis and data science.